

The Impact of Innovative Leadership in Enhancing Job Performance to Support Qatari Companies and Entrepreneurs: A Case Study of Qatar Development Bank

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the impact of innovative leadership on enhancing job performance in support of Qatari companies and entrepreneurs, particularly those supported by Qatar Development Bank. The research adopted a descriptive-analytical approach and utilized a randomly selected sample of 105 participants representing companies and entrepreneurs supported by the bank in Qatar during 2025. The primary data collection tool was a questionnaire developed based on previous studies and the theoretical framework.

The study found a significant positive correlation between innovative leadership and corporate support, specifically in the areas of product development, training, and financial assistance. The results also showed that innovative leadership has a statistically significant impact on supporting companies and entrepreneurs, by facilitating processes such as speed of service delivery, clarity of requirements, and time efficiency—factors reflecting communication flexibility and streamlined internal procedures.

These findings are valuable for leaders and decision-makers at Qatar Development Bank, as they provide actionable insights to enhance the support mechanisms offered to companies and entrepreneurs in Qatar.

Keywords: Innovative Leadership – Corporate Support – Entrepreneurs – Job Performance – Administrative Procedures

Introduction

Everything in the world is striving for continuous change, because today's era is characterized by great scientific and technological progress. We find major shifts in concepts that require changes in organizational structures, the work environment, and human relations. Companies and entrepreneurs are in dire need of renewal and change to keep pace with modernity and development. Since the world is interested in change for the better, humans must keep pace with the accelerating world in which they live and not remain stagnant or an obstacle to these developments. One of the most important characteristics of contemporary societies is their ability to innovate and create innovative mental states among individuals. With the emergence of many challenges such as globalization and intense competition between institutions, the need for innovation has emerged to keep pace with the developments of the era. Since the world has become a small village, administrative leaders in the field of business and companies must adopt mechanisms and ideas that encourage innovation to achieve creativity; to benefit from time and effort and manage the work of groups together. This requires a leader capable of influencing others; to optimally utilize their latent skills

and capabilities, understand environmental challenges, and understand contemporary needs to achieve the organization's goals. Therefore, innovative leadership requires leadership skills such as the ability to make decisions and employ creativity and innovation to generate knowledge to reach the right decisions for their organization. They must also possess perseverance and a strong awareness of the importance of achieving innovative leadership by creating a work environment and organizational climate that supports innovation, along with an effective incentive and reward system. The organization must also be decentralized, particularly in decision-making and problem-solving, allowing employees to present innovative ideas and avoid imitation. They must also utilize all that is new to improve and develop the efficiency of their employees, raising their performance and improving productivity. This will keep pace with the tremendous developments, and ensure that their organization, as a management, is always at the forefront. Innovative leadership is also considered an important and decisive factor in supporting Qatari companies and entrepreneurs in particular, increasing their competitiveness in the international and local markets in light of the rapid technological and economic changes. Qatari companies and entrepreneurs supported by Qatar Development Bank rely on visionary leaders who can adopt creative thinking and address the challenges facing entrepreneurship. Innovative leadership helps increase companies' resilience, enabling them to adapt to global economic changes and take advantage of promising opportunities in various sectors, such as advanced technologies and sustainability. By adopting an innovation-based approach, Qatari companies and entrepreneurs can develop services and products to meet market needs, contributing to sustainable expansion and growth.

Qatar Development Bank is a strategic partner in supporting innovative leadership within Qatar's business ecosystem. It provides several integrated financing and advisory solutions that help companies and entrepreneurs adopt innovative strategies that enable them to rise in the market. It also offers financial support programs, such as subsidized interest-bearing loans, to develop certain sectors that the country needs. The bank also contributes to promoting Qatari products at international exhibitions and forums through the Qatar Development Bank's export arm, Qatar Exports. Additionally, the bank contributes to fostering a culture of innovation in Qatari companies by offering programs and workshops aimed at developing leadership skills in creativity and innovation, helping companies enhance their competitiveness and benefit from modern technologies.

Research Problem:

The research problem is to define innovative leadership, its characteristics, and dimensions, and to understand its impact on enhancing job performance in supporting Qatari companies and entrepreneurs supported by Qatar Development Bank. Innovative leadership is considered one of the most important leadership approaches for economic growth, especially in the modern era, as a successful economy is built on adopting new ideas and innovative strategies to keep pace with rapid changes in the local and global market. Innovation has become a necessary, even mandatory, issue for companies, entrepreneurs, and institutions to ensure competitiveness, growth, and sustainability, especially in the era of globalization, rapid technological development, and increasing reliance on the digital and knowledge economy. Institutions, companies, and entrepreneurs are embracing creativity and innovation to achieve sustainable development and address challenges. Despite this, several companies and entrepreneurs still face challenges in implementing innovative leadership. This is due to several factors, such as a weak environment for research and development, a lack of funding,

and the lack of an innovative culture within the organization. This poses general challenges, including the need to strengthen the role of institutions that support entrepreneurship, such as banks and development institutions, to provide an appropriate environment for innovation and creativity (Al-Arini, 2022).

The Qatari economy, in accordance with the current development and economic vision, seeks to transform into a diversified economy based on knowledge and innovation, in accordance with Vision 2030. Therefore, the need to support innovation in leadership and entrepreneurship has emerged as an essential element of development. Despite the existence of several opportunities that support companies and entrepreneurs, they have faced several challenges and difficulties that hinder the widespread implementation of innovative leadership ideas. Prominent examples include the fact that Qatari companies may face challenges in obtaining adequate funding to implement their innovative projects, and that the infrastructure that supports research and development still needs greater support. In addition, Companies and entrepreneurs face challenges related to their ability to expand into global markets. This requires leaders with an innovative and strategic vision, the ability to adapt to global changes, and institutional support to achieve these goals (Abu Kishk, 2023).

Despite the significant efforts made by the government or its affiliated institutions that support innovation, such as the Qatar Development Bank, there is a need to expand the study of the impact of innovative leadership on Qatari companies and entrepreneurs. This is to determine the extent to which these companies and entrepreneurs can achieve actual sustainability by adopting innovative models in their businesses and determining the method by which they operate. Therefore, the key question here is how these types of companies and entrepreneurs interact with the changing business environment and how they respond to support and initiatives aimed at supporting innovation. Do companies have qualified human resources capable of leading their innovation processes? Do they have the capacity to overcome any operational and organizational obstacles they may face in the local or global market?

The study's main question is: What is the impact of innovative leadership on enhancing job performance in supporting companies and entrepreneurs, especially those supported by the Qatar Development Bank? This main question gives rise to several sub-questions that aim to clarify various aspects of the topic, including: What is innovative leadership? What are its main characteristics? And what is the degree to which Qatari companies and entrepreneurs practice innovative leadership in companies supported by the Qatar Development Bank? The study also seeks to understand these companies' and entrepreneurs' perceptions of innovative leadership and the extent to which a work environment that supports innovation enhances the support provided to them. In addition, the study examines the impact of innovative behavior and management's approach to employee engagement in supporting companies and entrepreneurs supported by the Qatar Development Bank. The study also addresses the obstacles and challenges facing the implementation of innovative leadership in Qatari companies. Finally, it seeks to determine whether there are statistically significant differences in the responses of the study sample regarding the degree of innovative leadership practice and the obstacles to its implementation due to demographic variables such as gender, educational qualifications, and years of experience.

Therefore, this study aims to examine the impact of innovative leadership on enhancing job performance and supporting Qatari companies and entrepreneurs backed by Qatar Development Bank. It explores the concept and characteristics of innovative leadership, its practice within supported companies, and the perceptions of beneficiaries. The study

also investigates how a supportive work environment, innovative behavior, and leadership interactions with employees influence organizational support. Furthermore, it identifies the challenges facing the application of innovative leadership and seeks to provide recommendations to decision-makers to improve the support provided to companies and entrepreneurs.

This study contributes to existing knowledge by addressing the role of innovative leadership in enhancing job performance and supporting Qatari companies and entrepreneurs backed by Qatar Development Bank. Theoretically, the study adds value by focusing on a critical area of leadership that influences support mechanisms for entrepreneurs, enriching academic literature with insights into the impact of innovative leadership. Practically, it offers benefits for researchers in the leadership field, especially given the growing need for innovative leaders capable of applying strategies that strengthen entrepreneurial support. The study also highlights the potential economic benefits of such leadership, including job creation and increased business opportunities. Additionally, it is expected to assist decision-makers at Qatar Development Bank in improving internal processes and to encourage further research connecting innovative leadership with other variables, offering conclusions and recommendations that enrich the field.

Study Variables and Model:

- Independent variable: Practice of innovative leadership at Qatar Development Bank.
- Dependent variable: Product development, training, and financial support.
- Intervening variable: Flexibility of communication and internal procedures, speed of achievement, and clarity of requirements.

Figure 1 (study variables and model)

Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Development

H1: Innovative leadership has a positive impact on enhancing job performance and supporting companies and entrepreneurs, especially those supported by Qatar Development Bank.

Innovative Leadership (Independent Variable):

The concept of innovation is one of the concepts that has faced difficulty in establishing a clear and unified definition. This is because it overlaps with many other concepts and is not limited to a specific field. There is innovation in education, innovation in technology, innovation in the economy, innovation in the business market, and others.

Each field has a different definition of innovation, but they all agree on the idea that innovation means the successful exploitation of new ideas and their transformation into new practices. In other words, it relies primarily on application (Mansour, 2019).

Innovation is also defined as a complex concept that combines decisions, characteristics, and personal traits, combined with a suitable environment. These traits elevate mental processes, producing original and novel ideas relative to the individual's or group's experience in the realm of human life (Jarwan, 2015). Therefore, it can be said that innovation refers to a leader's ability to come up with something new. To add greater value and more quickly than others, it is a set of activities implemented and applied to employees, assisting them in developing in-service training and education, which helps them advance in their work by leveraging their knowledge and experience (Al-Duwaik, 2020).

In this regard, it is noted that innovative leadership helps leaders bring about change for the better when implementing new innovative ideas. This is achieved by creating motivation and perseverance during work, as well as the ability to formulate new solutions to solve problems and make appropriate decisions to improve the work environment.

Innovative leadership is defined as leadership built on close relationships and connections among an organization's employees. It also leads to the development of work methods and the diversification of mechanisms and systems that encourage innovation and their use in achieving the organization's goals. It also implements innovative ideas on the ground and works to open channels of communication in all directions (Hanini, 2023). It is also defined as a set of practices of a scientific nature, aimed at creating greater effectiveness in work methods so that the organization can achieve its goals (Abu Ajwa, 2018). Innovative leadership is a set of methods, means, and approaches that a leader uses and adopts to achieve the organization's goals and address the problems and difficulties that may face it. It can be identified by innovative behavior, the work environment, and the leader's interactions with his subordinates (Hughes, 2018).

Innovative leadership is also defined as a leadership style characterized by creative vision and insight, and the ability to influence employees to generate and nurture innovative ideas to achieve the organization's desired goals (Abu Saleh, 2019). It is also defined as a set of leadership practices undertaken by the leader, relying on a creative vision based on generating and reorganizing leadership ideas. They also generate new ideas to achieve desired goals at the lowest cost and with the required high quality (Al-Ajouri, 2023).

It is concluded that innovative leadership reflects the leader's ability to employ innovative methods and ideas by building interactive relationships with the work team, striving to achieve excellence and institutional progress. Through a review of previous literature, the most prominent characteristics of innovative leadership are evident in the ability to inspire and motivate employees to adopt and effectively implement new ideas, while possessing a genuine desire for continuous development and embracing positive change. It is also characterized by building a distinctive network of collaborative relationships with employees that enhances mutual trust, along with a relentless pursuit of creative solutions to the organizational challenges and problems facing the organization. **The Importance of Innovative Leadership**

Innovative leadership is a fundamental pillar for organizations, contributing to achieving goals and enhancing competitiveness (Harzallah, 2015). Its importance lies in enabling work teams to develop work methods and increasing organizational

flexibility to adapt structures to future and emerging changes (Ghanem, 2018). It also enables organizations to adopt innovative standards to benchmark their performance against competitors and facilitates the elimination of routine procedures that hinder innovation (Al-Qadi, 2021). Furthermore, it improves the quality of internal systems, integrates modern technology, and supports change processes to keep pace with societal needs (Harzallah, 2015).

Innovative leadership is evident in fostering a spirit of creativity within organizations and stimulating unconventional initiatives based on knowledge and effective implementation (Ghanem, 2018). It also contributes to anticipating the future through shared visions, providing the necessary motivation for innovators, and developing new methods for developing intellectual skills (Al-Qadi, 2021). Thus, innovative leadership becomes a vital tool for achieving competitive advantage and ensuring sustainable growth.

Characteristics of Innovative Leaders

Innovative leaders possess personal, mental, and motivational traits that enable them to lead change and deal with challenges effectively, as explained by Al-Qadi (2021). They are characterized by self-confidence and the ability to achieve goals without resorting to authority, in addition to a willingness to take calculated risks. Mentally, they tend to think outside the box and seek unconventional solutions to problems. Motivationally, they are characterized by embracing challenges and avoiding routine, with a constant focus on renewal and innovation, as also confirmed by Ayyad (2019).

Innovative leaders also possess advanced capabilities, such as sensitivity to problems and their ability to anticipate them before they occur, flexibly reorganize ideas, deeply analyze situations, and evaluate solutions based on available capabilities (Ayad, 2019). Additionally, they possess a clear vision and the ability to build collaborative teams, with a focus on continuous learning and self-development. Dimensions of Innovative Leadership:

Innovative leadership relies on four main dimensions: (1) Fluency, which refers to the innovator's ability to generate the largest possible number of ideas in a limited amount of time (Al-Qatifan, 2020). This includes intellectual fluency (the ability to generate diverse ideas about a given problem), verbal fluency (producing words with clear meanings), expressive fluency (clearly formulating interconnected ideas), and associative fluency (connecting different ideas to find innovative solutions) (Al-Qatifan, 2020); (2) Originality, which refers to the ability to generate new and unfamiliar ideas (Abu Ajwa, 2018), enabling the leader to get to the root of problems, implement innovative and radical solutions, and avoid traditional solutions (Jaradat, 2012); (3) Flexibility, which refers to the ability to adapt to changing situations (Al-Duwaik, 2020), whether through adaptive flexibility (adjusting the approach to the situation) or spontaneous flexibility (spontaneously generating diverse solutions) (Al-Duwaik, 2020); (4) Sensitivity to problems, which is the ability to quickly detect problems, analyze challenges in unconventional ways, and predict problems before they occur (Jaradat, 2012). Together, these dimensions form an integrated framework for enhancing innovative performance in organizations.

The current study hypothesizes that innovative leadership positively impacts the support of companies and entrepreneurs, especially those supported by the Qatar Development Bank.

H2: Processes such as flexible communication, internal procedures, Speed of Achievement, and clarity of requirements facilitate product development, training, and financial support provided by Qatar Development Bank.

Job Performance (Dependent Variable):

Job performance is the total and expected value of what employees accomplish within a standard period. Outstanding job performance depends on the extent to which employees' energies and efforts contribute to achieving the organization's goals within available resources and capabilities. The concept of job performance is of paramount importance to decision-makers in organizations as it serves as a key criterion and indicator of the ability of organizations and their employees to achieve desired goals. This is based on employees' ability to complete job tasks, which reflects the overall level of job performance (Al-Malki, 2018).

Job performance is defined as the total work outputs achieved by employees, such as the quality of work, the required level, and the time and effort expended to complete that work. Although indicators are established for employees to adhere to, the competitiveness of any organization depends on the actual number of employees and effective job performance (Ramzy, 2018).

Job performance is defined as the sum of the efforts exerted by employees within organizations. It reflects the relationship between the number of employees and their job output, as well as the extent of an individual's commitment to completing assigned tasks efficiently. Job performance also refers to a set of professional behaviors that reflect an employee's ability to perform their duties and assume the responsibilities associated with their position. Job performance is one of the primary criteria for assessing the quality of work and the competence of individuals, as it helps determine the extent of an employee's commitment to responsibilities, how to develop their skills, and how to leverage previous experiences to improve overall performance, contributing to continuous development within the work environment (Ridwan, 2020).

Job performance is considered important and essential for both government and private institutions. Researchers have differed in their understanding of job performance, depending on their perspectives on the data and objectives they seek to achieve in their research, and their view of performance. Some have focused on achieving goals in light of performance results. It is the final result of an individual's activities and a reflection of the individual's ability and capacity to achieve the organization's goals (Hussein, 2023).

The importance of job performance is evident in its pivotal role in achieving institutional goals and improving organizational outcomes. It is a key indicator for measuring the efficiency and effectiveness of utilizing available resources within the organization. Job performance is not limited to assessing individual productivity; it constitutes an essential part of the integrated management process. Outstanding performance supports administrative decision-making based on precise criteria, which helps achieve organizational goals efficiently. Additionally, job performance plays a key role in improving and developing the work environment by identifying the challenges facing the organization, analyzing their causes, and proposing appropriate solutions to overcome them. This ensures continued development and the highest levels of productivity and quality (Hatamleh, 2019).

The importance of job performance is evident through a set of pivotal aspects that highlight its vital role in enhancing the effectiveness of institutions and achieving their goals, as explained by Hatamleh (2019). It contributes to improving internal

communications between employees and external communications with clients and stakeholders. It enhances the capabilities and energies of individuals to enhance organizational performance. It also helps identify programs, individuals, or projects worthy of funding. Job performance is the foundation upon which managers and supervisors rely when planning human resources and measuring their needs. It also focuses on efficiently achieving desired goals by providing a feedback system, analyzing deviations, and addressing them with effective corrective decisions. This performance is linked to the stages of an organization's development, from stability to leadership, making it essential to continuously monitor responsibilities and motivate employees. It also enhances employee self-awareness of their need to improve their performance through training and making professional decisions that support their development and the organization's success.

Job performance is affected by several key factors that contribute to its improvement or decline, as indicated by Al-Sarayrah (2022). One of the most prominent of these factors is the lack of clarity in objectives. Some organizations suffer from a lack of precise goal definition, which hinders directing employees toward achieving clear and measurable results. The lack of effective employee participation in development processes also impacts performance. Failure to involve employees in change leads to a gap between management and employees and a decline in teamwork. Lack of job satisfaction is a key factor affecting employee performance and productivity, requiring management to prioritize employee satisfaction as a means of motivating and enhancing efficiency. Furthermore, administrative laxity is a negative factor affecting performance, as working time is wasted on unproductive activities due to administrative shortcomings and a failure to monitor employee behavior. This threatens the effectiveness of organizations and leads to a decline in their performance.

Key Elements of Job Performance

1. Product Development

Product development is an essential component of improving services and products, as companies strive to keep pace with changing market needs and technological developments. This development relies on understanding customer requirements through market research and collaboration between different departments, such as research and development and marketing. The process also requires effective project management and adopting a culture that encourages innovation and calculated risk-taking. Balancing innovation, quality, cost, and speed to market is crucial to a company's success and enhancing its competitive position (Mohammed, 2015; Basir, 2018).

2. Training

Training is a vital tool for human resource development, as it aims to improve skills, knowledge, and behaviors to meet current and future requirements. The objectives of training include changing individual behavior, increasing loyalty to the organization, and improving overall performance. The effectiveness of training depends on good planning, identifying needs, designing appropriate programs, and evaluating results. A training strategy is an essential part of an organization's plans, as it contributes to enhancing competencies and meeting future challenges (Sassi, 2017; Ahmed, 2014; Abdul Razzaq, 2012).

3. Financial Support

Financial support is the backbone of any project or institution, whether it's financing daily operations or investing in development and innovation. Sources of financial support include bank loans, investments, and government grants. Providing adequate and timely financing is crucial to business success, ensuring its sustainability, and its ability to compete in the market (Markan, 2018; Qashi, 2017).

Administrative Procedures (Mediating Variable):

Administrative procedures represent a set of rules and steps adopted within an organization to carry out its regular and repetitive activities and tasks in a consistent and organized manner. These procedures include a number of procedures and processes, such as hiring, purchasing, and expenditures, as well as records, documents, customer service, and other procedures. The primary objective of establishing administrative procedures is to ensure efficiency and effectiveness in procedures and standardize the way tasks are performed. This is to ensure the quality of processes and outputs, reduce errors, and facilitate the training of new employees. This also ensures compliance with the organization's regulations, laws, and policies, and enhances accountability and oversight within the organization. The existence of effective and clear procedures significantly contributes to organizing work, facilitating flow, and achieving stability (Idris, 2020).

For administrative procedures to be effective and useful, they must have several characteristics, most notably clarity and simplicity, making them easy to understand and implement by all relevant employees. They must also be well-documented and readily available to those who need them. These procedures must also be practical, applicable, and directly linked to achieving business objectives. However, the business environment is characterized by constant change, which necessitates periodic review and updating of administrative procedures to ensure they remain relevant and effective and do not hinder productivity or innovation. Procedures that may have been appropriate at a particular time may become bureaucratic, complex, or irrelevant as technology advances, business strategies change, or more efficient ways of performing tasks emerge. Therefore, organizations must strive to continually simplify and improve their procedures to ensure they remain supportive of high performance and the ability to quickly adapt to changes (Idris, 2020).

Flexibility of Communication and Internal Procedures:

Communication is a fundamental element in organizations that facilitates workflow. Therefore, communication must be flexible between different sectors and individuals within the organization, and this communication must be appropriate at the appropriate time, in different situations, for the target audience, and for the intended message. Communication can be done through formal or informal means, whether written or verbal. Communication flexibility is of great importance in a diverse and rapidly changing work environment. It contributes to fostering mutual understanding between teams and individuals, fostering cooperation among all, and solving problems quickly. It also increases an organization's ability to adapt to new developments and strengthens internal relationships between organizations, their clients, and partners, ultimately leading to a more productive work environment (Khuwaildi, 2017). Communication flexibility is demonstrated through a number of practices within an organization, including the use of a variety of communication channels, such as chats, emails, various types of meetings, or phone calls, and choosing the appropriate time for each situation. It also includes the ability to modify the content of the message to suit the recipient, and it encourages open dialogue and two-way feedback, rather than being limited to

top-down directives. Application flexibility also requires good communication and providing employees with the necessary training and tools to enhance communication skills and enable them to choose the appropriate communication methods for their situations. However, it requires finding a balance to avoid chaos (Janad, 2020).

Speed of Achievement:

Although several individuals are equal in their abilities, skills, and experience to complete a specific task or perform a specific job, there is a disparity between them in terms of their level of performance. This disparity is due to differences in individuals' motivation to work and the strength of their desire to accomplish this task or job. Motivation is an internal force within a person that directs behavior to satisfy a specific need. If this need is not satisfied, a type of stress occurs within the individual. This need may be internal, such as self-actualization, or external, such as the desire for promotion or financial incentives. Achievement motivation is a topic that has been widely researched recently (Al-Zaidi, 2024).

Achievement motivation refers to the internal drive that drives individuals and workers to continue performing their tasks efficiently, enhancing their ability to achieve desired goals. The importance of this motivation lies not only in its impact on the psychological aspect of individuals, but also extends to many applied fields, such as economics, management, and education. Achievement motivation is also a key element in stimulating productivity and enhancing performance. The higher the level of this motivation in individuals, the greater their ability to innovate and excel, which contributes to improving the work environment and achieving sustainable growth within various organizations. Achievement motivation and its importance contribute to raising the level of individual or worker performance and increasing their productivity in all fields and activities. The higher the levels of achievement motivation for individuals, the greater their productivity. This, in turn, is reflected in the economic growth of societies as a whole, as the rise or fall in overall economic growth is sometimes linked to the rise or fall in the level of individual motivation and productivity. The importance of achievement motivation is also evident in an individual's awareness, attention, and focus on memory and thinking processes. It also helps individuals increase their knowledge, empowers them to behave well in various circumstances and situations, and helps enable them to be influenced by others, especially in competitive situations. This makes it easier for them to understand others, interpret their behavior, and thus predict it (Al-Mutairi, 2019). Achievement motivation plays a pivotal role in guiding and activating individual behavior. It directly influences an individual's perception of the various situations they encounter and is a prerequisite for initiating the learning and awareness process, as Zenati (2015) pointed out. It helps individuals understand their own behavior, enhances their integration with the surrounding factors and circumstances, and simultaneously works to raise their performance and productivity in the work environment.

The level of achievement among individuals is influenced by several factors, the impact of which varies from person to person. This depends on the influence of a single factor or a combination of factors, as Al-Saqa (2018) explained. These factors include the quality of values prevalent in society, the social role the individual plays, their level of intelligence, and the extent of their interaction with the group. These factors also include socialization methods, previous experiences of success or failure, and finally, the degree of attractiveness and importance of work to the individual. These factors

collectively form the basis that determines their level of achievement and the nature of their performance.

Clarity of Requirements:

Clarity of requirements in organizational work means that the goals, tasks, expectations, and specifications specified for any project, process, or product are clearly understood and free from any misinterpretation or ambiguity by all stakeholders. This includes defining what is required to be accomplished, the criteria for success and quality, and the constraints and resources available. Clarity of requirements is a cornerstone of any successful endeavor, significantly reducing the likelihood of misunderstandings, errors, rework, and resource waste. When requirements are clear, individuals and teams can effectively direct their efforts, develop accurate plans, and correctly estimate the necessary resources. This leads to more efficient implementation and the achievement of the desired results with higher quality and on time (Hashem, 2023).

Achieving clarity of requirements requires proactive effort and effective communication. The process often begins with comprehensively gathering information from all relevant stakeholders and accurately understanding their needs and expectations. These requirements should then be formulated in simple, straightforward, and specific language, avoiding vague or technical terms that are difficult for everyone to understand. Using visual aids such as diagrams and prototypes can help clarify complex ideas. It is also essential to formally document requirements and share them with all stakeholders to ensure their understanding and agreement. Clarity of requirements does not stop at the initial definition; any changes to the requirements must be managed systematically and communicated to everyone, ensuring all parties remain on the same page to achieve alignment and shared success (Al-Dosari, 2024).

Therefore, the study assumes processes such as flexible communication and internal procedures, Speed of Achievement, and clarity of requirements, which facilitate product development, as well as training and financial support provided by Qatar Development Bank.

3. Methodology

The descriptive-analytical approach was chosen as the primary methodological framework for this study due to its suitability to the nature of the research topic and its objectives. This approach is one of the most widely used scientific approaches in social and administrative studies, which aim to examine phenomena as they exist in reality and analyze them in a systematic manner that enables understanding their various dimensions. This approach is based on two main stages: The first stage involves a detailed description of the phenomenon under study—innovative leadership in the context of supporting companies and entrepreneurs—as it appears in the targeted Qatari community. This is achieved by collecting, classifying, and analyzing relevant data and information in a systematic and organized manner. The second stage is analysis, which is conducted across two integrated levels: qualitative analysis, which focuses on aspects that cannot be measured numerically, such as leadership traits and practices, and innovative approaches, by monitoring the contexts, interactions, and surrounding factors. Quantitative analysis relies on figures and statistical indicators derived from research tools, represented by using tables and graphs to illustrate the prevalence of the phenomenon, measure its impact, and uncover general trends related to it.

This approach is distinguished by its ability to link the various dimensions of the phenomenon, enabling it to analyze the interrelationships between them and several other relevant variables, such as the level of institutional support, type of leadership,

field of economic activity, and other factors that may directly or indirectly affect the effectiveness of innovative leadership. This approach also allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study within its real-world context, without subjecting it to abstract theoretical assumptions. This gives the research results greater reliability and realism, and makes the recommendations derived from it more applicable in practice. It is worth noting that the choice of this approach was not random but rather based on a review of previous literature that addressed similar topics. The descriptive-analytical approach has proven effective in providing clear and in-depth insights into administrative and economic phenomena, particularly in dynamic environments influenced by multiple internal and external factors, such as the Qatari business environment. Therefore, employing this approach in this study will contribute to arriving at accurate results that reflect reality and provide decision-makers with the necessary information to develop policies and strategies that support innovative leadership in both the public and private sectors.

Study Population and Research Sample:

The study includes the research population, represented by individuals from companies and entrepreneurs supported by the Qatar Development Bank in the State of Qatar. The researcher seeks to generalize the results to this target population. The study relied on a random sample from this population to ensure its representation of the characteristics of the original population. The sample included individuals from companies and entrepreneurs dealing with the Qatar Development Bank during the year 2025. In accordance with the specified sample selection criteria, the final sample size reached 105 individuals.

Description of the characteristics of the research sample:

Frequencies and percentages were calculated for the research sample individuals according to the following variables:

Table 1:

Demographic Characteristics of the Study Sample

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	83	79%
	Female	22	21%
	Total	105	100%
Age	Under 30 years	4	4%
	30-40 years	48	46%
	40-50 years	36	34%
	Over 50 years	17	16%
	Total	105	100%
Education Level	High school	8	8%
	Bachelor's degree	59	56%
	Master's/PhD	38	36%
	Total	105	100%
Work Experience	3-7 years	8	8%
	More than 7 years	97	92%
	Total	105	100%

The analysis results show that the study sample consisted of 79% males and 21% females. In terms of age distribution, the 30-40 age group represented the largest proportion (46%), followed by the 40-50 age group (34%), while the over-50 age group comprised 16% of the sample. The younger age group (under 30) was the least represented at only 4%. Regarding educational level, those with a bachelor's degree had the highest percentage (56%), followed by those with a master's degree or doctorate

(36%), while high school graduates constituted 8% of the sample. Regarding work experience, the results showed that the vast majority (92%) of the sample had more than 7 years of experience, compared to only 8% with 3-7 years of experience.

Data Collection Tools:

The study relied on a questionnaire designed based on a review of a number of previous studies to define dimensions and formulate statements. The questionnaire included two main sections: the first was devoted to demographic data such as gender, age, educational level, and professional experience, while the second section included seven main sections measuring the study variables: innovative leadership, clarity of requirements, Speed of Achievement, time, product development, training, and financial support. This provided a comprehensive tool for collecting the data necessary for the study.

Validity and Reliability of the Data Collection Tool:

After the researcher drafted the questionnaire in its initial form, based on the theoretical framework and objectives of the study, it was necessary to ensure that the research tool met the requirements for validity. This ensured its ability to accurately and objectively measure the intended variables. Validity of the study tool means that the items and phrases contained in the questionnaire clearly express what they were designed to measure and that they reflect, to a high degree, the content of the variables and concepts related to innovative leadership and entrepreneurial support.

To verify the validity of the questionnaire, the researcher relied on the "face validity" method, also known as "reviewer validity," a common method in social studies, to verify the appropriateness of the tool's content. The questionnaire was presented in its initial form to a group of judges and specialists with experience and knowledge in fields related to the study topic. Among them were a number of officials from Qatar Development Bank, given their direct knowledge of the nature of support provided to companies and entrepreneurs and related leadership practices. The reviewers were asked to provide their opinions and comments on the clarity of the items, their relevance to the study's objectives and main themes, as well as the accuracy of the wording and correctness of the language. Based on the comments and suggestions received from these reviewers, the researcher made the necessary modifications to the questionnaire's content, either by deleting some phrases, rephrasing others, or adding new items that would contribute to improving the tool's coverage of the study's areas. In this way, the final version of the questionnaire was achieved, which was approved and included in the appendices of this study, reflecting a reliable and valid research tool that effectively measures the targeted variables.

Data Collection Tool Reliability:

To verify the reliability of the study tool, the researcher tested its reliability using Cronbach's Alpha, one of the most common and accurate statistical methods for measuring the internal consistency of a research tool, particularly in questionnaires that rely on a multi-item Likert scale. This procedure aims to ensure that different statements measuring the same dimension or latent variable yield similar results. This means that the tool is capable of measuring what it was designed to measure with high reliability and consistency when repeated under similar conditions.

The questionnaire was administered in its semi-final form to a preliminary sample of (15) participants, with the aim of conducting a preliminary test of the internal consistency of the statements. Using the statistical analysis program (SPSS), Cronbach's Alpha was calculated for each of the questionnaire's axes separately, as well

as for the entire tool. The resulting values indicate the degree of correlation between the statements within each axis, with values exceeding (0.70) being considered a good indicator of high reliability. The following table shows the results of the reliability test, indicating the values for each dimension of the questionnaire. This confirms that the study tool has a high degree of internal consistency, which enhances the reliability of the results that will be reached through subsequent statistical analysis.

Table 2:
Questionnaire Reliability Coefficient (Internal Consistency)

Dimension	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha (Internal Consistency)
Innovative Leadership	4	0.895
Clarity of Requirements	4	0.886
Speed of Achievement	4	0.906
Time	4	0.903
Product Development	3	0.900
Training	4	0.915
Financial Support	4	0.929

The previous table shows that the overall validity of the questionnaire is excellent. Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the dimensions ranged between 0.886 and 0.929, while the coefficient value for the entire questionnaire was 0.972. This indicates the validity of the questionnaire for use in research purposes and to achieve the study's objectives.

Statistical Analysis:

The study relied on statistical analysis using the SPSS program to analyze the data. The collected data was converted to numerical values and entered into the program to obtain statistical results, which included calculating frequencies and percentages for the initial data and questionnaire statements, in addition to calculating standard deviations and arithmetic means for the various dimensions. Pearson's correlation coefficient and simple and multiple linear regression analysis were used to study the relationships between the various research variables.

Analysis and Discussion of Results

This section discusses the results of the statistical analysis conducted on the data collected using the questionnaire. The data was analyzed using SPSS, where a set of statistical operations were applied to determine the relationships between the various variables. This analysis was divided into several sections that address the study of the research variables, testing the hypotheses, and presenting the results obtained. The study focused on the relationship between innovative leadership and the support provided to companies and entrepreneurs supported by Qatar Development Bank, exploring in-depth the impact of several factors, such as Speed of Achievement, clarity of requirements, and time on this relationship. Advanced statistical methods, such as Pearson's correlation coefficient and simple and multiple regression analysis, were used to test the study's hypotheses.

Study of Research Variables:

Based on the conscious knowledge of the characteristics of the study sample, the questionnaire was designed for the study and to describe trends. Below, we review the descriptive analysis of the variables, which is a statistical method used to interpret

related coefficients, which have different implications for the variables. The following table shows the arithmetic mean and standard deviation, which reflect the opinions of bank customers regarding this study:

Table 3:

Arithmetic Means and Standard Deviation of Questionnaire Dimensions

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Innovative Leadership	3.95	0.829
Clarity of Requirements	3.84	0.779
Speed of Achievement	4.063	0.942
Time	3.72	0.827
Product Development	4.014	0.710
Training	3.74	0.920
Financial Support	3.90	0.734

The average of respondents' opinions is strongly disagreed when it ranges from 1 to 1.8, the average of respondents' opinions is disagreed when it ranges from 1.81 to 2.6, the average of respondents' opinions is neutral when it ranges from 2.61 to 3.4, the average of respondents' opinions is agreed when it ranges from 3.41 to 4.2, and the average of respondents' opinions is strongly agreed when it ranges from 4.21 to 5.

From the results of the previous table, we find that the sample members' opinions agree with the study dimensions, with the averages ranging from 3.74 to 4.063 for all dimensions. This indicates the importance of the study dimensions (innovative leadership, clarity of requirements, Speed of Achievement, time, product development, training, and financial support). The standard deviation values ranged from 0.710 to 0.942, which are small values, indicating the extent of the sample's opinions' consensus.

- Independent variable: Innovative leadership (first hypothesis) - (Speed of Achievement - clarity of requirements - time as an indicator of "flexibility of communication and internal procedures") - second hypothesis.

- Dependent variable: Support for companies and entrepreneurs, which includes product development, training, and financial support.

Presentation and Discussion of Study Results:

The study hypotheses were tested using one of the most important statistical methods, namely Pearson's correlation coefficient and simple and multiple regression, as follows: Pearson's correlation analysis is a procedure used to measure the strength of the relationship between two continuous variables. This analysis measures the degree of association between a pair of variables, where the correlation coefficient is calculated, ranging from $(-1 < r < 1)$. Correlation analysis is used as part of multiple linear regression analysis as a pre-test to assess the strength of the relationship between each explanatory variable and the response variable. It can also be used to identify variables that can be used in multiple linear regression analysis.

Table 4:

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient for Study Variables

	Innovative Leadership	Clarity of Instructions	Speed of Achievement	Time	Support of Companies
Innovative Leadership	1	.743**	.718**	.706**	.752**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
Clarity of Instructions	.743**	1	.793**	.796**	.732**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000

	Innovative Leadership	Clarity of Instructions	Speed of Achievement	Time	Support of Companies
Speed of Achievement	.718**	.793**	1	.882**	.707**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
Time	.706**	.796**	.882**	1	.756**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
Support of Companies	.752**	.732**	.707**	.756**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the previous table, it is clear that there are significant relationships between the corporate support variable, which contains (training - product development - financial support), and each of the innovative leadership variable and the process facilitation variables, which include clarity of requirements, Speed of Achievement, and time, which reflects the extent of flexibility of communication and internal procedures, as (Sig=0.000<0.01) for all variables, and as the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient ranges between (0.707-0.756), i.e. greater than 0.60, and the direction of the relationship is direct, since the sign of the correlation coefficients is positive.

Testing the Study's First Hypothesis:

In our current study, simple regression analysis was first used to test the study's first hypothesis: "Innovative leadership positively influences support for companies and entrepreneurs, especially those supported by Qatar Development Bank." As a statistical method, we analyzed the linear relationship between the independent variable (innovative leadership) and the dependent variable (support for companies and entrepreneurs, which includes product development, training, and financial support). This method determined whether there was a significant effect between the two variables using:

- Correlation coefficient value: R.
- Explanatory power of the model using the coefficient of determination: R^2 .
- Model significance level: P-value <0.05.

The degree of influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is determined based on the beta value. The following tables illustrate the results of the regression analysis:

Table 5

Summary of the Linear Regression Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.752 ^a	.565	.561	.48600

a. Predictors: (Constant), Innovative Leadership

Table 6 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the model

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	31.642	1	31.642	133.965	.000 ^b
Residual	24.328	103	.236		
Total	55.970	104			

a. Dependent Variable: Support of Companies

b. Predictors: (Constant), Innovative Leadership

Table 6*Linear regression coefficients*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	1.266	.232		5.452	.000
Innovative Leadership	.665	.057	.752	11.574	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Corporate Support

From the previous tables, we find that:

- The correlation coefficient between the corporate support variable and the innovative leadership variable is 0.752, indicating a direct correlation between the two variables.
- The coefficient of determination for the model is 0.565, meaning that changes in innovative leadership explain 56.5% of the changes in corporate support.
- The P-value is <0.05, indicating that the model is statistically significant.
- The degree of influence of innovative leadership on support for Qatari companies and entrepreneurs is 0.665.

From the previous results, there is a statistically significant effect of innovative leadership on corporate support among employees in the banking sector, confirming the study's first hypothesis: "Innovative leadership positively influences support for companies and entrepreneurs, especially those supported by the Qatar Development Bank.

Testing the Second Hypothesis of the Study:

To verify the second hypothesis of the study, "Processes such as flexibility of communication and internal procedures, Speed of Achievement, and clarity of requirements facilitate product development, training, and financial support provided by Qatar Development Bank.", three multiple regression analysis models were used, adding each of the following three variables separately:

1. Speed of Achievement.
2. Clarity of requirements.
3. Time as an indicator of the extent of "flexibility of communication and internal procedures."

The aforementioned regression model was used to verify the first hypothesis. To clarify the impact of these processes on the significance of the relationship between corporate support and innovative leadership, the following tables illustrate the results of the regression analysis:

1. Speed of Achievement:

Table 8*Summary of the Linear Regression Model*

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.806a	.650	.626	.42243

Predictors (Constant): Speed of Achievement, Innovative Leadership

Table 9*Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the model*

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.623	2	4.812	26.964	.000b
	Residual	5.175	29	0.178		
	Total	14.798	31			

Dependent Variable: *Corporate Support*
 Predictors: (Constant) *Speed of Achievement*

Table 10
Linear regression coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Standardized Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig
1 (Constant)	0.466	0.482	—	0.966	0.342
<i>Innovative Leadership</i>	0.571	0.078	0.833	7.330	0.000
<i>(Speed of Achievement)</i>	0.192	0.083	0.261	2.301	0.029

a. Dependant Variable: *Corporate Support*

From the previous tables, we find that:

- The model's correlation coefficient is 0.806, indicating an increase in the model's correlation level compared to 0.752 in the previous model.
- The model's coefficient of determination is 0.65, meaning that changes in innovative leadership and speed of implementation explain 65% of the changes in corporate support, which is greater than the explanatory power of the previous model, which was 56.5%.
- The P-value is <0.05, indicating that the model is statistically significant.
- The degree of influence of innovative leadership in this model is 0.571, which is a decrease from the previous model, which was 0.665, while the degree of influence of speed of implementation was 0.192.

From the above results, we conclude that speed of implementation has an impact on the relationship between corporate support and innovative leadership. Adding the speed of implementation variable to the relationship between corporate support and innovative leadership increased the model's correlation coefficient and its explanatory power. The model was also significant, confirming the validity of the study's second hypothesis.

2. Clarity of requirements:

Table 11
Linear regression model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.795a	.632	0.632	0.625

Predictors: (Constant) *Innovative Leadership*, Clarity of Requirements

Table 12
Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the model

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	35.396	2	17.698	87.746	.000bb
	Residual	20.573	102	.202		
	Total	55.970	104			

a. Dependent Variable: *Corporate Support*
 b. Predictors: (Constant), *Innovative Leadership*, Clarity of Requirements

Table 13
Linear regression coefficients

Model 1	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig
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Constant	Constant	0.872	.233	—	3.739	0.000
(Innovative Leadership)	(Innovative Leadership)	0.411	.079	0.464	5.170	0.000
(Clarity of requirements)	(Clarity of requirements)	0.365	.084	0.387	4.315	0.000

Dependent Variable: Corporate Support

From the previous tables, we find that:

- The model's correlation coefficient is 0.795, indicating an increase in the model's correlation level compared to 0.752 in the previous model.
- The model's coefficient of determination is 0.632, meaning that changes in innovative leadership and clarity of requirements explain 63.2% of the changes in corporate support, which is greater than the explanatory power of the previous model, which was 56.5%.
- The P-value is <0.05, indicating that the model is statistically significant.
- The degree of influence of innovative leadership in this model is 0.411, which is a decrease from the previous model, which was 0.665, while the degree of influence of clarity of requirements was 0.365.

From the above results, we conclude that clarity of requirements has an impact on the relationship between corporate support and innovative leadership. Adding the variable of clarity of requirements to the relationship between corporate support and innovative leadership increased the model's correlation coefficient and its explanatory power. The model was also significant, confirming the validity of the study's second hypothesis.

3. Time:

Table 14:

Linear Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R ² (Adjusted)	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1	.817	.667	.660	.42751

a. Predictors: (Constant), Time, Innovative Leadership.

Table 15

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the model

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
Regression	37.327	2	18.664	102.116	.000**
Residual	18.642	102	0.183		
Total	55.970	104			

a. Dependent Variable: Corporate Support

b. Predictors: (Constant) Time, Innovative Leadership

Table 16

Linear regression coefficients

Predictor	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t-value	p-value
(Constant)	0.894	—	4.161	<.001***
Innovative Utility	0.384 (±0.071)	0.434	5.385	<.001***
Time	0.399 (±0.072)	0.450	5.577	<.001***

Dependent Variable: Corporate Support

From the previous tables, we find that:

- The model's correlation coefficient is 0.817, indicating an increase in the model's correlation level compared to the previous model's 0.752.

- The model's coefficient of determination is 0.667, meaning that changes in innovative leadership and time explain 66.7% of the changes in corporate support, which is greater than the explanatory power of the previous model, which was 56.5%.
- The P-value is <0.05 , indicating that the model is statistically significant.
- The degree of influence of innovative leadership in this model is 0.384, which is a decrease from the previous model's 0.665, while the degree of influence of time was 0.399.

From the above results, we conclude that there is a time effect in the relationship between corporate support and innovative leadership. Adding the time variable, which reflects the flexibility of communication and internal procedures, to the relationship between corporate support and innovative leadership increased the model's correlation coefficient and its explanatory power. The model was also significant, confirming the validity of the study's second hypothesis. From the results of the three previous regression models, the second hypothesis of the study can be confirmed: "Processes such as flexibility of communication and internal procedures, Speed of Achievement, and clarity of requirements are facilitated by product development, training, and financial support provided by Qatar Development Bank."

Findings

The analysis results showed a significant, direct relationship between innovative leadership and corporate support. It was proven that innovative leadership positively impacts product development, training, and financial support. Factors such as Speed of Achievement, clarity of requirements, and time, which reflect flexibility in communication and internal procedures, also played a significant role in facilitating internal processes and enhancing corporate support.

The innovative leadership hypothesis was tested through simple regression analysis, and the analysis demonstrated that innovative leadership positively impacts corporate support. The facilitation of internal processes hypothesis was also tested using multiple regression analysis, and the results showed that influential factors such as Speed of Achievement, clarity of requirements, and time contribute to product development and the support provided.

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis revealed strong significant relationships between innovative leadership variables and administrative procedures such as clarity of requirements and Speed of Achievement. The correlation coefficient values ranged between 0.707 and 0.756, indicating a strong direct relationship. Simple and multiple regression analysis models were used to test the relationship between innovative leadership and corporate and entrepreneurial support. The results showed that changes in innovative leadership explained approximately 56.5% of the changes in corporate support.

When variables such as speed of achievement, clarity of requirements, and time were included, the explanatory power of the statistical models increased to between 65% and 67%. The addition of these variables contributed to increasing the effectiveness of the statistical model, strengthening the validity of the second study hypothesis related to facilitating internal processes.

Recommendations:

Financial institutions, such as Qatar Development Bank, should foster innovative leadership within their teams to support the operations and services provided to Qatari companies and entrepreneurs. This can be achieved by adopting innovative management strategies that enhance their ability to adapt to change and achieve effective results. Facilitating internal communication and simplifying administrative

procedures are essential elements that contribute to accelerating decision-making and reducing the time required to complete tasks, leading to improved effectiveness of the support provided.

In this context, it is important to improve the clarity of the requirements presented by institutions to clients and companies. This ensures a clear vision and contributes to more effective organization of operations, reducing the potential for confusion and facilitating the implementation of required tasks. It is also recommended to develop mechanisms to accelerate the implementation of projects and operations within financial institutions by increasing operational efficiency and relying on modern technologies that support faster and more accurate business completion.

Enhancing specialized training programs for employees is a necessary step to develop their skills in innovation, team leadership, and handling advanced administrative processes, which positively impacts the quality of institutional performance. Furthermore, investing in information technology and smart systems represents a strategic tool for accelerating internal procedures, as modern software systems contribute to improving operational efficiency and accurate decision-making. It is also important to foster a culture of innovation within the organization by encouraging employees to present new ideas and create a work environment conducive to innovation. This contributes to raising organizational performance and achieving sustainable development. Finally, a continuous evaluation system must be in place to assess the performance and effectiveness of internal processes, as well as the factors influencing product development and financial support, ensuring continuous improvement of processes and their efficient implementation.

Research Limitations:

Research limitations include a set of organizational and individual factors that may influence the study's results. At the organizational level, the different organizational structures within banking institutions play an important role in how innovative leadership is implemented and how companies are supported. Some institutions may have flexible structures that support an innovative environment, while others may adhere to traditional structures that limit opportunities for innovation. Furthermore, divergent internal policies among banks may affect the speed of implementation and clarity of requirements, negatively impacting the effectiveness of innovation in supporting companies. Furthermore, the ability to provide financial support is an important organizational aspect that may hinder the implementation of studied strategies in some institutions. On the individual level, the differing views of banking sector employees regarding the concepts of innovation and its role in enhancing institutional performance pose a challenge that must be taken into account when analyzing the research results.

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